

GENESIS AND PROVISIONS OF ARTICLE 370 AND 35A

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The Genesis

1. The genesis of Article 370 goes back to **Govt of India Act, 1935** passed by the British govt to give new adm dimension to the country as an improvement on Govt of India Act, 1919 by intro all India federations, provisional autonomy and the removal of the diarchy at the provincial level. It was also the last constitution of British India, before Indian Independence Act of 1947 and mainly framed from the Nehru Report, Lothian Report, Simon Commission Report, the White papers and the Jt Selection Commission Report. However, diarchy at the Cent govt formed the main comp wherein the subjects under the federal list were divided into two main cat- of Res and Transferred.

2. The res subjects were cont by the Governor-Gen who adm them with the help of three counsellors appt by him and were not resp to the legislature. These subjects incl Def, Ecclesiastical affairs (church-related), ext affairs, Press, Police, Taxation, Justice, Power resources and tribal affairs (*contextual to Article 370*). The transferred subjects were adm by the Governor-Gen with his Council of Min (not more than 10). The Council had to act in confidence with the legislature. The subjects in this list incl local govt, forests, edn, health, etc. However, the Governor-Gen had 'spl powers' to interfere in the transferred subjects also¹.

3. As per the act, the **Princely States accession to the federation was voluntary. The terms on which a state joined the "Federation of India" were to be laid down in an inst of Accession**", the rts and obligations of the British crown in respect of the Indian states were

¹ Pleaders Intelligent Legal Sols, Govt of India Act, 1935, By Anubhav Pandey - July 2, 2018.

to remain unaffected (*contextual to Article 370*). The rts and obligations were left in charge of the Crown Rep. It was permissible to combine the office of Governor-Gen and Crown Rep in the same person². Govt of India Act, 1935 de-facto became the principle docu for governance and legal auth on every subject in 1947, for both the dominions.

4. **Indian Independence Act, 1947.** The Indian Independence Act was passed on 18 July 1947 after scraping Cabinet Msn Plan fwg disagreements betn Indian National Congress and Muslim League. Under the provns of Indian Independence Act, 1947, the **Govt of India Act, 1935 governed the two newly formed dominions until their new constitutions were framed**. The British adm also appt a Governor Gen in both the dominions with primary resp to preside over the div of territories, rts, duties, powers, liabilities, assets, etc. The Governor Gen was also empowered to adopt and amend the 'Govt of India Act' 1935. The Princely States became indep and all the powers ex by British Auth were terminated. All treaties and agreements made by the British with ref to States would lapse from 15 Aug 1947. The princely states were free to associate themselves with either the Dominion or to remain indep. **The act was finally repealed in Article 395 of the Constitution of India of 1950 and in Article 221 of the Constitution of Pak of 1956³**. Therefore, voluntary accession to either dominion through Inst of Accession became mandatory.

5. **Inst of Accession.** Continuation of the provns of Govt of India Act, 1935 as per Indian Independence Act, 1947 influenced the drafting of Inst of Accession (IoA) for not only J&K but other princely states as well in 1947. On comparison of the four IoAs of Mysore, Manipur, Tehri Garhwal and Udaipur, it has come to lt that **all 140 princely states that signed IoAs with India agreed to the same terms and conds as J&K**. All these rulers also initially acceded to India ltd to the same three subjects. The remaining powers were retained by them just as the Maharaja of J&K had sought to do⁴.

6. Dr Karan Singh, the then yuvaraj of J&K, issued a proclamation on 25 Nov 1949 stating that the soon-to-be-adopted Constitution of India would govern the relationship betn J&K and India only to such extent as its provns would apply to J&K. Article 306A was thus conceived which would later become Article 370 and laid down the terms and conditions of this relationship⁵. **Article 306A dealt with powers of certain states in Part B of the First**

² Main Provns of the Indian Act of 1935 and Its Achievements, Article shared by: Mr SPriyadarshinj

³ My India, What Was the Indian Indep Act of 1947? Pub on: July 3, 2018 | Updated on: July 19, 2019

⁴<https://www.thewire.com> - The Backstory of Article 370: A True Copy of J&K's Instrument of Accession, sourced from the National Archives of India, accessed on 26 Aug 19.

⁵ *ibid.*

Schedule to impose rests on trade and commerce and was subsequently repealed by the Constitution (7th Amdt) Act, 1956, Sec 29 and schedule⁶.

Constituent Assy

7. **Indian Constituent Assy.** The idea of Constituent Assy of India was first put fwd by Shri MN Roy (CPI) in 1934. In 1935, it became an official demand of Indian National Congress which was accepted on 08 Aug 1940 and constituted under the Cabinet Msn plan on 06 Dec 1946⁷. It consisted of 389 members out of which 292 members were from provinces, 93 from princely states, three from Chief Commissioner Provinces and one from Baluchistan. In Jun 1947 delegations from Sindh, East Bengal, Baluchistan, West Punjab and the North West Frontier Province withdrew to form the Constituent Assy of Pak and the str was further reduced to 299 members (229 from provinces and 70 from princely states). **Though Constituent Assy finalised the Constitution of India on 26 Jan 1950 but provns related to citizenship, elections, Provisional Parliament, etc came into eff on 26 Nov 1949.** The Constituent Assy itself became provisional parliament of India till gen elections were held in 1952⁸.

8. **State's Constituent Assy.** All the princely states were invited to send reps to India's Constituent Assy, or set up their respective constituent assy. Most states responded in time and majority of the recoms were incorporated in the Indian Constitution as per the preamble and all states agreed to have a common constitution. **J&K along with many other princely states chose to form their own Constituent Assy and requested for applicability of only those provns of the Indian Constitution that corres to the original IoA and the state's Constituent Assy, when formed, would decide on the other matters.** Govt of India agreed to the demands and Article 370 was incorporated into the Indian Constitution, which stipulated that the other articles of the Constitution that gave powers to the Cent Govt would be applied to J&K only with the concurrence of the State's constituent assembly.

9. **J&K Constituent Assy.** National Conf (NC), the largest party headed by Sheikh Abdullah, announced on 27 Oct 1950 its decision to convene a Constituent Assy for J&K and the elections took place in Sep – Oct 1951 with a nominal membership of 100 members, of which 25 seats were allocated to Pak occu Kashmir (which were never filled) and of the remaining 75 seats, Kashmir was allocated 43 seats, Ladakh 2 seats and Jammu 30 seats. All the 43 seats of Kashmir went to the NC, two seats in Ladakh went to Head Lama, Kushak

⁶<https://www.legalindia.com> - Legal India, LegalNews&Law Resource Portal, accessed on 25 Aug 19.

⁷<https://www.gktoday.in/gk/the-constituent-assembly-of-india/>, accessed on 10 Sep 19.

⁸<http://www.quickgs.com/facts-about-constituent-assy-of-india-members-list/>, accessed on 11 Sep 19.

Bakula and in Jammu, 13 candidates belonging to the Jammu Praja Parishad had their nominations rejected and later they boycotted the elections, two indep candidates dropped out at the last moment, giving NC a clean sweep in State Constituent Assy elections. **The J&K State Constitution was adopted on 17 Nov 1956, which officially came into eff on 26 Jan 1957 and dissolved itself on the same very dayw/o recom either abrogation or amdt of the Article 370⁹.**

10. As J&K Constituent Assy shaped the state constitution, the domestic politics under Nehru – Sheikh Abdullah alliance outlined numerous pol initiatives and presidential orders to set stg for spl treatment of the state. Therefore, it is imp to analyse them to est their link with the pol devp of J&K over the last seven decades. These are enumerated in succeeding paras.

11. **Imp Articles.** It is imp to understand certain pertinent articles in the Constitution of India as given below for a holistic understanding: -

(a) **Article 238.** It articulates the provns dealing with the **adm of states in Part B of the First Schedule of Indian constitution** (In 1950, the Constitution contained a fourfold cl of the states of Indian union-Part A, Part B, Part C, Part D states). The Article was **abrogated in 7th Constitutional Amdt Act, 1956** in the wake of reorg of the states.

(b) **Article 368.** It lays down the procedure of constitutional amdts as laid down in Part XX of the Constitution of India. This procedure ensures the sanctity of the Constitution and keeps a check on arbitrary power of the Parliament of India. Although Parliament must preserve the basic framework of the Constitution, **there is no other limitation placed upon the amdt power and No of amdt in a specific pd, thus ensuring that there is no provn of the Constitution that cannot be amended.**¹⁰

(c) **Article 371.** It guarantees **spl privileges to Ten Indian States due to their peculiar character** on issues like social and religious practices, customs, land laws, distr of resources & funds, etc. It cannot be equated with Article 370 as it **does not provide any spl constitutional provns** and is applicable in Maharashtra & Gujrat (371), Nagaland (371A), Assam (371B), Manipur (371C), Andhra Pradesh

⁹https://howlingpixel.com/i-en/Constituent_Assy_of_J&K, accessed on 12 Sep 19.

¹⁰<https://www.legislative.gov.in> - "Constitution Amendment: Nature and Scope of the Amending Process" (PDF). Lok Sabha Sectt. Archived from original (PDF) on 3-12-13. Retrieved 1-12-13, accessed on 26 Aug 19.

(371D&E), Sikkim (371F), Mizoram (371G), Arunachal Pradesh (371H) and Goa (371 I)¹¹.

12. **Article 370.** The purpose of Article was to shield the state from complete appl of all the provns of the Constitution of India till the formation of J&K State Constitution. Therefore, the provns under **Article 370 were intended to be transitional and temp in nature under Part XXI of the Constitution of India** (which deals with Temp, Transitional and Spl Provns). The article was reqd to be abrogated/ ceased before terminating the State Constituent Assy. The Article was initially drafted by Sheikh Abdullah in 1947, who wanted permanency of the Article to have '**Iron Clad Autonomy**', which the PM Jawahar Lal Nehru disagreed¹². It was finalised by Gopalaswami Ayyangar, a Minister w/o portfolio in the first Union Cabinet of India and a former Diwan to Maharajah Hari Singh of J&K. Fwg certain mod and negotiations, Article 306A (now Article 370) was passed in the Indian Constituent Assy on 27th May 1949 and finally incl in the Constitution of India on 17th Oct 1949¹³.

13. The **Govt of the State till 1950 meant Maharaja of J&K** on the advice of Council of Ministers and **post 1952, it meant Sadr-i-Riyasat (now Governor)** on the advice of Council of Ministers¹⁴. The provns of Article 238 were not applicable in the state of J&K (though later revoked). As per **para 3 of Article 370, the President through a notfn could abrogate this article after the recom of the Constituent Assy of the State**. However, the State's Constituent Assy dissolved itself on 26th Jan 1957 w/o recom either abrogation or amdt of the Article. Thus, the Article took a '*perceived perm t stature*' of the Indian constitution, also est by various rulings of the Supreme Court and the High Court of J&K, the latest one being in April 2018¹⁵.

14. **Presidential Orders.** When Article 370 was originally created, only two articles of the Indian Constitution applied in full to J&K. Other provns of Indian Constitution applied with exceptions and mod specified in series of Presidential Orders with the concurrence of J&K govt. Imp presidential orders are as given below: -

¹¹<https://www.raiot.in/what-is-article-371-of-the-indian-constitution>, accessed on 24 Aug 19.

¹²<https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/What-is-Article-370Article-370/articleshow/35678708>, TNN Updated: Aug 3, 2019, 18:47 IST.

¹³<https://indianexpress.com/article/explained/understanding-articles-370-35a-jammu-kashmir-indian-constitution-5610996/>, accessed on 25 Aug 19.

¹⁴Cottrell, Jill (2013), "Kashmir: The vanishing autonomy", in Yash Ghai; Sophia Woodman (eds.), *Practising Self-Govt: A Comparative Study of Autonomous Regions*, Cambridge University Press, pp. 163–199, doi:10.1017/CBO9781139088206.006, ISBN 978-1-107-29235-2, accessed on 12 Sep 19

¹⁵<https://www.theecontimes.com> - Article 370, granting spl status to the state, is perm t: J&K High Court, 11 Oct 15. <https://www.thehindu.com> - The imp of Article 370, 15 Oct 15, accessed on 21 Aug 19.

(a) **Presidential Order – 1950.** Issued on 26 Jan 1950, the **Constitution (Appl to J&K) Order, 1950 deals with the partial appl of the provns of Indian Constitution to the State J&K.** 235 articles of the Indian Constitution were inapplicable to the state of J&K, nine were partially applicable, and 29 were applicable in a mod form. 38 subjects from the Union List and 10 of the 22 parts of the Indian Constitution were extended to J&K, with mod and exceptions as agreed by the J&K State Govt. This order was superseded by the Presidential Order of 1954¹⁶.

(b) **Presidential Order – 1952.** Issued on 15 Nov 1952, at the request of the state Govt, it amended the Article 370, replacing the phrase “recog by the President as the Maharaja of J&K” by “recog by the President on the recom of the Legislative Assy of the State as the Sadr-i-Riyasat”. The **amdt rep the abolition of the monarchy of J&K**¹⁷.

(c) **Presidential Order – 1954.** Issued on 14 May 1954 with the agreement of J&K State’s Constituent Assy, it was a comprehensive order seeking to **impl the 1952 Delhi Agreement** with fwg provns¹⁸: -

- (i) **Article 35A** was intro.
- (ii) **Fundamental rts** of the Indian Constitution extended to J&K.
- (iii) **Jurisdiction of the Supreme Court** of India extended to J&K.
- (iv) Cent Govt given power to **declare national emergency** in the event of ext aggression and for internal disturbances only with the concurrence of the State Govt.

15. **1952 Delhi Agreement.** The agreement betn the Govt of India and the J&K Constituent Assy in 1952, was later on known as the "Delhi Agreement, 1952",. The agreement was a precursor to the upcoming Article 35A on the spl rts and privileges. It had fwg provns¹⁹: -

- (a) **Sovereignty on all matters** except in the ‘Inst of Accession’ rested with the State.

¹⁶"The Constitution of India (1949)"(PDF). Lok Sabha Secretariat. pp. 1122–1123. Archived from *the original*(PDF) on 3 Dec 2013, accessed on 12 Sep 19.

¹⁷ *ibid*.

¹⁸http://jklaw.nic.in/constitution_jk.pdf, accessed on 12 Sep 19.

¹⁹[https://www.satp.org/satporgtp/countries/india/states/jandk/documents/papers/delhi Agreement-1952.htm](https://www.satp.org/satporgtp/countries/india/states/jandk/documents/papers/delhi%20Agreement-1952.htm), accessed on 26 Aug 19.

- (b) **Spl rts and privileges incl citizenship** were conferred as per J&K State's pre-independence notfns of 1927 and 1932 on domicile incl citizenship to Pakistanis.
- (c) **Separate Flag** for J&K State.
- (d) **Powers of Sadar – I – Riyasat or Governor** severely curtailed.
- (e) Appl of **Fundamental Rts, Article 352, 356 and 360** on emergency, suspension of State Constitution and fin emergency were conditional.
- (f) **Supreme Court had only appellate jurisdiction** in the State.

16. **Article 35A.** A final nail in the coffin, Article 35A was a **provn incorporated in the Constitution of India giving the J&K Legislature a carte blanche to decide who all are 'permt residents' of the state and confer on them spl rts and privileges** in public sect jobs, acqn of property in the State, scholarships and other public aid and welfare w/o being challenged for violating the Constitution or any other law of the land. Article 35A was incorporated into the Constitution by a Presidential Order - 1954 on the insistence of the Jawaharlal Nehru w/o any Parliamentary debate/approval.

17. The controversial Article fwg the 1952 Delhi Agreement extended Indian citizenship to the 'State subjects' of J&K²⁰. The Presidential Order was issued under Article 370 (1)(d) which allows the President to make certain exceptions and mods to the constitution for the benefit of state subjects²¹. It has been brought about by the executive organ when actually the rt of amdt of the Constitution lies with the legislative organ, which could be done only by the Parliament as per procedure laid down in Article 368. Therefore, it is, allegedly, ultra vires the basic structure of the Constitution, since it violates the Constitutional procedures est by law, as Article 35A was never presented before the Parliament.

18. **Amdts to J&K Constitution.** Indian Parliament has witnessed 103 constitutional amdts since 1950 under the provns of Article 368²². Similarly, J&K Legislative Assy has also impl 34 constitutional amdts in the J&K State Constitution of 13 Parts and 158 Secs, more or less mirroring the amdts in the Indian Constitution. **Part XII, Sec 147 of the Constitution of J&K** lays down the provns to amend J&K Constitution by introducing a Bill in the Legislative Assy of J&K and passing it in each House by a majority of not less than two thirds of the total membership of that House, before presenting it to the Sadar-i-Riyasat for

²⁰<http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/articleshow/68148587>, What is Article 35A? Updated: Feb 25, 2019, 11:57 IST, accessed on 26 Aug 19.

²¹<https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/what-is-article-35a/article19567213.ece>, accessed on 01 Sep 19.

²²<https://www.india.gov.in/my-government/constitution-india/amendments?page=9>, accessed on 03 Sep 19.

his assent and final amdt. However, amdots like change in this sect, Provns of sec 3 and 5 and Provns of the Constitution of India as applicable, in relation to the state cannot be made²³. First J&K Constitutional Amdt Act (CAA) was carried out in 1959 and in 1965, under 6th CAA, the names of Sadar-i-Riyasat and PM of J&K were changed to Governor and Chief Minister, respectively. In 1975, under 12th CAA, 24 seats were allocated to Pak occu Kashmir. Intro of 7th Schedule of Indian Constitution, reducing voting age from 21 to 18 yrs, incr salaries of Judges in 2018, extn of the powers of the Supreme Court and Election Commission to J&K, are some of the CAA of J&K, which have been mirrored on the amdots in the Indian Constitution. **Presidential Orders and J&K CAA highlight the legal route available to carryout desired amdots in J&K State Constitution with requisite pol manoeuvring.**

²³http://www.jklegislativeassembly.nic.in/Costitution_of_J&K.pdf, P 66, pp 147, Part XII, accessed on 03 Sep 19.